

Automated CANDU Refuelling with NESTLE-C

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ABSTRACT

CANDU reactors are refuelled multiple times per week while operating at full power. The selection of fuel channels to be refuelled requires a delicate balancing of power distributions and reactivity control devices. A Python tool has been developed which automates this process for the NESTLE-C full core diffusion code. The tool scores refuelling candidate channels and attempts to refuel the highest ranked, thereafter manipulating reactivity control devices to achieve power balance. This allows long periods of operation to be simulated, providing viable reactor states which can be used, for example, for training machine learning algorithms. The tool was used to simulate 30 years of operation in which channels were refuelled at, on average, 99% of maximum burnup while maintaining an average reactor power of 95% full power.

Keywords: CANDU, Refuelling, NESTLE-C, Diffusion, Reactor Physics

1. INTRODUCTION

CANDU (CANada Deuterium Uranium) reactors are cooled and moderated with heavy water and usually operate using natural uranium (NU) fuel. The fuel is assembled in a cylindrical cluster bundle of approximately 0.5 m in length. The reactor is laid out in a rectangular lattice of horizontal pressure tubes, each typically containing 12 bundles. This design allows CANDU reactors to be refuelled while operating at full power. Refuelling is performed constantly over multiple days each week. Each refuelling operation involves shifting fresh fuel (typically 8 bundles) into a channel and removing the same number of spent fuel bundles from the other end [1]. As a result of the low reactivity NU fuel, regular use of burnable poison is not required, and reactivity peaks are controlled using computer-controlled devices. The Liquid Zone Controls (LZC), the workhorses of CANDU operation, are a set of 14 vertical tubes arranged inside the core which can be filled with light water [1]. Light water has relatively higher neutron absorption than heavy water, which allows the LZCs to fine-tune the flux and power distribution.

Because of regular on-power refuelling, the burnup distribution in a CANDU reactor is very heterogeneous. Adjacent channels are refuelled in opposite directions, which results in a more uniform axial power distribution across the core [1]. Refuelling operations are crucial to counter-balancing the negative reactivity from burnup. The selection of channels to be refuelled is therefore key to maintaining a uniform core and avoiding derating (i.e., power reductions). Channel selection for refuelling relies on a combination of simulations and the expertise of the station physicists. Full core simulations using a neutron diffusion code, which can be used to follow the reactor in real time (so-called core-follow simulations) are carried out constantly using reactor monitoring data and predictive burnup calculations.

This paper describes a Python tool developed for the NESTLE-C diffusion code [2] which automates the process of burnup advancement, channel selection, refuelling, and liquid zone control balancing. NESTLE-C is a CANDU-specific fork of the original NESTLE code [3] developed at North Carolina State University, owned by

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the Canadian regulator, the Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission (CNSC) and maintained by Canadian Nuclear Laboratories (CNL). It has the capability to perform instantaneous and transient core calculations but does not natively support refuelling or channel selection. The latest version of NESTLE-C developed at CNL (v. 3.1.3) also re-incorporates light water reactor modelling capability.

The refuelling automation tool described in this paper evolved from an early version developed as part of previous work [4], where it was used to generate instantaneous burnup distributions representing regular operational states. The goal of the earlier was to generate training data for a machine learning emulator estimating loss of coolant accident outcomes, using the generated reactor states as initial conditions. The current version was a significant expansion and formalization, developed with the goal of more accurately representing real-life operation.

2. METHODOLOGY

The reference CANDU design used for this work was the 380-channel CANDU-6, the parameters of which are provided in *Table I*. These parameters are user-configurable and can be modified based on the reactor model. NESTLE-C v. 3.1.3 was used with the Finite Difference Method (FDM) solution mode. Two-group cross sections were generated previously [5] [6] using Serpent 2.1.29 with a continuous energy library based on ENDF/B-VII.0.

Table I. CANDU-6 Parameters.

Parameter	Value	Units	Parameter	Value	Units
Thermal Power	2061.4	MW _{th}	Lattice pitch	28.575	cm
Fuel channels	380	-	Bundle length	49.53	cm
LZC units	14	-	Bundle heavy element mass	19.1	kg
Bundles per channel	12	-	Average discharge burnup	7.5	MWd/kg

2.1. Description of algorithm

The NESTLE-C refuelling tool operates by first generating a time-averaged bundle-power distribution (described in section 2.2) along with burnup limits for every bundle position. It then reads all user-specified parameters from a configuration file before beginning a day-by-day simulation over the user-defined time span.

On non-refuelling days (Tuesdays, Thursdays, Saturdays, and Sundays) the tool initializes a new daily simulation, advances time and bundle burnup by one day, executes NESTLE-C, attempts to balance the LZC levels (section 2.4), and applies reactor derating if necessary (section 2.5).

On refuelling days, the tool performs a set number of refuelling operations (user-configurable, and in this case set to five on Mondays and Wednesdays and four on Fridays). For each refuelling operation, it initializes the day's simulation, advances burnup on the first operation only, runs NESTLE-C, and checks whether the k_{eff} exceeds the target, skipping refuelling for that day if so. It then evaluates pre-refuelling bundle powers and scores all channels according to defined refuelling criteria (section 2.3). The tool repeatedly attempts refuelling by selecting the highest-scoring channel, performing the refuelling, and re-balancing LZCs. If the attempt fails, the channel is excluded, and the process continues with the next candidate. After exhausting the allowable number of refuelling attempts (set by the user), the tool derates the reactor and resumes the channel-selection loop until a successful refuelling is achieved.

2.2. Time-Averaged Power Distribution

Time-averaged power calculations are typically performed for CANDU reactors to account for the continuous changes in core configuration due to online refueling and to provide a steady-state approximation of core behavior. This involves averaging burnup distributions over possible refuelling patterns to estimate quasi-equilibrium bundle powers. NESTLE-C does not itself have a time-averaged power calculation mode. Instead, the DONJON code [7] was used to generate burnup limits (i.e. burnup values immediately before and after a refuelling operation at each bundle position). A channel refuelling order was generated based on a set pattern (as described in [8]), and in conjunction with the burnup limits was used to generate 380 burnup distributions, each iteration representing a

burnup state immediately after refuelling one of the channels in order. The resulting power distributions after running each burnup distribution with NESTLE-C were averaged to estimate a time-averaged power distribution.

2.3. Channel Selection Algorithm

The criteria for refuelling channel selection were based on those described in [1]. The procedure is:

1. Eliminate channels where the channel power is greater than the (user-defined) margin to the (user-defined) maximum channel power, and the eight channels surrounding them.
2. Eliminate the last 10 channels to be refuelled and the four channels surrounding them.
3. Eliminate channels where the average exit burnup of the last 8 bundles are less than 0.9 times the upper burnup limit for those bundle positions.

All remaining channels are scored using Equation (1). The selection of the scoring formulation, namely the included parameters, and their relative weighting via their exponents, was empirically determined through iterative testing with the refuelling algorithm. The configuration described below performed effectively in maintaining the reactor power balance in successive refuelling operations.

$$score_i = (CP_{max} - CP_i) \left(CPPF_{max} - \frac{CP_i}{CP_{TAVG,i}} \right) \left(\frac{LZC_t}{LZC_{z(i)}} \right) (T_h \log \ell_{h,i}) (T_v \log \ell_{v,i}) \left(\frac{\sum_{j \in [-8:]} BU_{i,j}}{\sum_{j \in [-8:]} BUL_{i,j}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where the terms of the product are:

- The maximum channel power (user-defined to 7.3 MW) minus the channel power of channel i
 - Results in higher score for lower power channels and a negative score for channels exceeding the power limit.
- The maximum channel power peaking factor (user defined to 1.1) minus the channel power peaking factor (CPPF - ratio of channel power to time averaged channel power) for channel i
 - Results in higher score for channels with lower CPPF
- The ratio of the target LZC level (user defined to 0.5) to the level of the LZC near channel i
 - Results in lower score for channels in zones where the LZC levels are higher (i.e. where there is less control margin for excess reactivity)
- The horizontal power tilt multiplied by the log of the horizontal location of channel i
 - Results in lower score for channels located horizontally on the same side as the power tilt
- The vertical power tilt multiplied by the log of the vertical location of channel i
 - Results in lower score for channels located vertically on the same side as the power tilt
- The square of the ratio of the average exit burnup of the bundles in channel i to be refuelled (i.e., the last 8 in this case) and the upper burnup limit for those bundle positions
 - Results in higher scores for higher burnup channels. This component is squared to increase the importance of high burnup.

2.4. Liquid Zone Control Adjustment

The LZC level adjustment is performed iteratively, attempting to equalize the ratios of zone power (the sum of channel powers across an LZC “zone”) to time-averaged zone power across all of the zones. As shown in Figure 1, the channels are mapped into zones based on proximity to each of the 14 LZC units. There are 7 zones covering the “front” half of the reactor (i.e. bundles 1-6) and 7 further zones covering the “back” (i.e. bundles 7-12).

The adjustment algorithm first sets all LZC levels to 0.5 (i.e. halfway full). It then uses the zone power ratios to adjust the levels by an empirically-derived sigmoid function:

$$lzc_1 = lzc_0 + (zpr - 1) \frac{\sqrt{1 - \frac{k}{4}}}{\sqrt{1 - k \left(\frac{zpr - 1}{w} \right)^2}}, \quad lzc_1 = \begin{cases} lzc_{min} & lzc_1 < lzc_{min} \\ lzc_{max} & lzc_1 > lzc_{max} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where lzc_0 is the LZC level (for a given zone) at the previous iteration; lzc_1 is the calculated value for the current iteration; lzc_{min} and lzc_{max} are the minimum and maximum allowed values for LZC level (0.1 and 0.9 respectively); and zpr is the zone power ratio of the zone. The width factor w is set to 0.25 and the sharpness k is set to 0.95. This function is plotted over a range of initial level values (lzc_0) and zone power ratios (zpr) in Figure 2, where the initial level occurs at $zpr = 1$ (i.e. the LZC level does not change at this value). This function is intended to make smaller fine-tuning adjustments when zpr is close to 1 and make exponentially larger changes to LZC level as the zone power ratio approaches the extremes.

2.5. Derating

As described in section 2.1, when liquid zone control iteration is insufficient to evenly distribute reactor power, and the maximum number of refuelling attempts is reached, the total reactor power is decreased (the reactor is “derated”). The decrease in power is calculated by first determining which LZC iteration over all of those attempted resulted in the smallest maximum bundle and channel powers. The ratio of the maximum channel and bundle powers from that iteration to the respective power limits is used as the derating factor. Total reactor power is then reduced to $0.99 \times \text{derating factor} \times \text{nominal power}$, and refuelling is attempted again on the channel which corresponded to the selected iteration.

Figure 1. Mapping of the 14 zones to CANDU fuel channels (reactor front shown in XY axis)

Figure 2. Adjustment of liquid zone control level based on the zone power ratio.

3. RESULTS

Evaluating the performance of the refuelling algorithm required verifying that it could maintain stable power balance, keep the reactor critical, and achieve average nominal burnup over a long period of time. To test the current version, a refuelling simulation was executed for 30 consecutive years of operation time. Over this period, 18,788 refuelling operations were performed. One of the burnup distributions from the time-average calculation was initially used as a starting point, and refuelling was performed for two years. The resulting burnup distribution was used at the initial state for the long-term refuelling test.

The refuelling frequency of each channel over this time is shown in Figure 3. The effect of the reactivity control devices can be observed, particularly in the relatively lower frequencies in the middle of the core. This area contains the largest concentration of reactivity control devices (in particular, the adjusters) and thus operates at lower relative power. The power and therefore the rate of burnup in the surrounding ring is relatively higher than

the centre of the core, resulting in a higher refuelling frequency. Another effect of the reactivity control devices and their support structures (located in the top half of the reactor) is a slight vertical tilt. It can be seen that channels at the top of the reactor are refuelled slightly less frequently than those at the bottom (which operate at higher relative power). The skew in vertical powers can also be seen in the plot of vertical power tilt vs. time (Figure 4b). The trend for horizontal tilt is shown in Figure 4a and can be observed to be relatively even.

Channels were refuelled at a minimum of 95% of the nominal maximum burnup of the last 8 bundles (those being removed from the core). This was a hard-coded limit within the code, and as can be seen in Figure 5, this resulted in the majority of refuelling operations taking place at around 95% full burnup. Nevertheless, the mean burnup of refuelled channels was 99.2% of nominal. This is an area for improvement in future iterations of the algorithm.

The most difficult parameter to balance in the refuelling simulation is the distribution of bundle and channel powers. This is mostly achieved by manipulation of the liquid zone controls, with the goal of maintaining the maximum bundle and channel powers below their respective license limits (935 kW and 7.3 MW, respectively). The code also enforced a 2.5% margin to the maximum channel power limit, and a 5% margin to the maximum bundle power limit. These limits and margins are defined in the user configuration. The maximum bundle and channel powers at each day are shown in Figure 6. The mean bundle and channel powers over the simulation period were 835.3 +/- 17.0 kW and 6.7 +/- 0.1 MW, respectively.

When the maximum powers could not be sufficiently suppressed by iteration of liquid zone controls, the total reactor power reduced, as described in section 2.5. The total power trend over the simulation period can be seen in Figure 7. The mean total power over the simulation was 1955.6 +/- 46.1 MW. This is another area for improvement. Ideally, the simulations should not need to rely on derating the core to remain below the maximum power margins and further refinement of the algorithm should aim to achieve a total reactor power closer to the nominal full power (2061.4 MW).

Overall, though there are areas for improvement, the refuelling algorithm was effective in maintaining stable reactor operation, within desirable margins for power balance, average burnup, and total power generation.

Figure 3. Refuelling frequency of each channel over 30 years of operation

Figure 4. The horizontal (a – left) and vertical (b – right) power tilt at each day during the simulation period.

Figure 5. Histogram of burnup of refuelled channels, as a percentage of nominal maximum burnup.

Figure 6. Maximum bundle (a – left) and channel (b – right) powers at each day during the simulation period.

Figure 7. Trend of total reactor power (% of full power) over the simulation period.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A Python tool was developed for the automation of CANDU burnup and refuelling with the diffusion code NESTLE-C. The tool advances time and burnup, selects a channel to refuel, and performs the refuelling, and subsequently manipulates the reactivity control devices to level the power distribution in the core. It repeats this process for a given simulation length. A simulation of 30 years of consecutive operation was performed with the tool. Over this period, the reactor power was maintained on average at about 95% of full power, and channels were refuelled at, on average, 99% of their nominal maximum burnup. Further work, described in the next section, is needed to continue to refine the algorithms to attain higher average power.

4.1. Future Work

In the future, the refuelling program is intended to be further optimized. The liquid zone control level adjustment algorithm should be further optimized to reduce the number of necessary iterations, thereby speeding up the simulations. The current iteration of the program relies on derating the core to maintain channel and bundle powers below license limits. Further development of the channel selection scheme is needed to reduce this reliance and ensure the nominal power level is maintained for most of the operation time. Both of these areas for improvement may benefit from the application of machine learning tools, trained on the large dataset that has been generated, to make more optimized channel selections. Finally, the performance of the refuelling program should be compared against station data from one of the operating CANDU plants.

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